

SPATIAL AND TEMPORAL DYNAMICS OF OLIVE QUICK DECLINE SYNDROME IN PUGLIA, SOUTHERN ITALY

M. MONTES-BORREGO¹, M. MORELLI², L. SUSCA³, D. BOSCIA², M. SAPONARI², B. B. LANDA¹, J. A. NAVAS-CORTES^{1*}

¹INSTITUTE FOR SUSTAINABLE AGRICULTURE, CSIC, CORDOBA, SPAIN. ²CNR ISTITUTO PER LA PROTEZIONE SOSTENIBILE DELLE PIANTE (IPSP), SS BARI, ITALY. ³DIPARTIMENTO DI SCIENZE DEL SUOLO, DELLA PIANTA E DEGLI ALIMENTI, UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI BARI ALDO MORO, BARI, ITALY.

***Corresponding author: j.navas@csic.es.**

The spatial dynamics of Olive Quick Decline Syndrome (OQDS) caused by *Xylella fastidiosa* subsp. *pauca* are being determined in 20 olive plots in a selected olive growing area within the infected zone of the Lecce province in Puglia by the IAS-CSIC team in collaboration with CNR-UNIBA by assessing disease incidence and severity (on a 0-5 rating scale) by the end of June, 2016. Of them, eight plots with a wide range of initial disease incidence and severity values were selected for further analyses in early October 2016 to assess the spatial and temporal dynamics of the OQDS in Puglia region. Data analyses are in progress and include the use of the Spatial Analysis by Distance Indices (SADIE) to quantify the spatial pattern of OQDS incidence and severity. The spatial association between the two time periods was analyzed using the SADIE association Index that measures the local association between clustering indices of both time periods. The spatial pattern of symptomatic olive trees was estimated as regular (22.2% of plots), non-aggregated (33.3% of plots) or aggregated (44.4% of plots). Both, disease incidence and severity increased in the second assessment in all plots by an average of $28.7 \pm 4.2\%$ and 0.53 ± 0.27 , respectively. The spatial pattern was characterized by the occurrence of several clusters of infected trees. Increasing clustering over the two time periods was indicated by stronger values of clustering index over time and by the increase in the size of patch clusters. A significant spatial association was found in the clustering of diseased trees over time.